

UNIVERSITY OF GOTHENBURG

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES

A BRIEF APPROACH TO THE INTEGRATION OF ICT IN LEARNING ACTIVITIES

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Guest Researcher at University of Gothenburg (Sweden) Spring Term, 2014

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SOCIAL CONTEXT

Technology and Information are two of the more representative concepts defining our society. Why?

- **Information:** There is a large amount of information flowing across the world, and it has become a great resource
- **Technology:** We are living in constant contact with them. They allow us to connect, communicate, inform, etc., making our lives easier.

If we relate both concepts, we notice that most things around us are influenced by information, technologies, or both.

Our society has changed in the last decades. Since the 1970s, these changes have been so substantial that we could talk about global social change and the development of a new society.

We can remember the slogan “Information is power” and the role of the media in cases that produced social, economic, or political changes.

Some examples:

- Pentagon Papers; 1971. The USA. Vietnam War. Lying about the reasons for entering the war.
- Watergate; 1975. The USA. Political spying. Resignation of the US President, Richard Nixon.
- Iraq War; 2003; USA/UK/Spain/Portugal. J. Wilson reports no evidence of the existence of mass destruction weapons or that Iraq purchased uranium to develop them.
- Climagate; 2009. It published information about manipulating data on the effects of global warming by a scientific group.
- Wikileaks & Snowden Cases.
 - In 2010, Wikileaks (Julian Assange) revealed data and activities of the U.S. Army in the Iraq War.
 - In 2013, The Guardian and The Washington Post revealed information, facilitated by Snowden, about the mass

surveillance programs of US intelligence agencies (FBI & NSA). Pulitzer Prize 2014.

- Politician resignations:
 - German Ministers accused of plagiarism (2013; Annette Schavan y 2009; Karl-Theodor zu Guttenberg)
 - Jérôme Cahuzac (2014), French Finance Minister, due to have accounts in Switzerland (Tax haven)
 - Maria Miller (2014), the UK Culture Minister, resigns due to possible excessive expenditure on accommodation.

These cases were possible due to access to information. ICT has helped spread information and contributed to social changes. It makes the world flatter and helps to build the Information Society.

Information Society is a new social configuration in which information (related to aspects of generation, processing, storage, and dissemination) becomes the main social axis. The information turns the processes of society's economic, social, and political development (Baelo & Cantón, 2010).

But in the last decades, this definition has suffered changes, and now we advocate for a society where knowledge will substitute information as a central axis of development.

The “brain work” replaces “manual work”

EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

We work with the citizens of this Society, and we must take part in their learning process to develop the skills and competencies that this Society requires. Our students are different and live in a different context. They are **digital natives**, and they have different characteristics.

What is the research telling us about digital natives?

- a) The student's attention capacity has not changed.
- b) They use different parts of the brain to process the information.
- c) The style of digital natives processing information has changed even though they process the same information.

Digital natives want to

- a) Be an active part of their learning process.
- b) Learn in a collaborative environment.
- c) Learn with tools that they use in their life.
- d) Develop a functional learning.
- e)

<i>Digital learners prefer</i>	<i>Many educators prefer</i>
Receiving info quickly from multiple multimedia sources	Slow and controlled release of info from limited sources
Parallel processing and multi-tasking	Singular processing and single or limited tasking
Processing pictures, sounds, colors, and video before text	To provide text before pictures, sounds and video
Random access to hyper-linked multimedia information	To provide info linearly, logically, and sequentially
To network simultaneously with many others	Students to work independently before the network and interact
To learn "just-in-time" to teach "just-in-case". Instant gratification and immediate rewards	Deferred gratification and delayed rewards

Learning that's relevant, active,
instantly useful and fun

Feel compelled to teach to the
curriculum guide and tests

We cannot allow us to teach in the same way as we have been taught.
We must take advantage of the tools around us to change and improve
our teaching methods, and ICT is one of these tools.

For this purpose, we should change our methodologies to:

1. Show the possibilities and risks that have the tools used
in the daily lives of our students.
2. Give tools to our students to process and transform the
information.
3. Teach to catch, collect, store, and produce the
information.

KEY COMPETENCIES

There is no universal definition of 'key competence'. The OECD's Definition and Selection of Competencies (DeSeCo) Project provided a developmental framework for defining key competencies.

Competency is more than just knowledge and skills. It involves the ability to meet complex demands by drawing on and mobilizing psychosocial resources (including skills and attitudes) in a particular context. For example, the ability to communicate effectively is a competency that may draw on an individual's knowledge of language, practical ICT skills and attitudes towards those with whom he or she is communicating (OECD, 2001).

DeSeCo Project (OECD, 2005) gave us a general framework, which is the basis of the document "Key competencies for lifelong learning" (European Union, 2006). European Union (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2012) considers that key competencies are essential *skills* and *attitudes* for Europeans to succeed in *today's economy, modern society, and their personal lives*.

In recent years, the concept of key competencies has gained prominence among European education systems. Most European countries have made significant progress in incorporating the key competencies into national curricula and other steering documents.

Key competencies should be acquired by:

- Young people at the end of their compulsory education and training are equipped for adult life, particularly for working life, while forming a basis for further learning.
- Adults, throughout their lives, go through a process of developing and updating skills.

The acquisition of key competencies fits in with the principles of equality and access for all. This reference framework also applies to disadvantaged groups whose educational potential requires support.

Examples of such groups include people with low basic skills, early school leavers, the long-term unemployed, people with disabilities, migrants, etc.

At the EU level, eight key competencies have been defined, representing a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes considered necessary for personal fulfilment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion, and employment. These competencies are (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2012):

- Communication in the mother tongue
- Communication in foreign languages
- Mathematical competence and basic competencies in science and technology
- Digital competence
- Learning to learn
- Social and civic competences
- Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship
- Cultural awareness and expression.

DIGITAL COMPETENCE

There are many definitions of digital competence. We will use one from the European Union. From the EU perspective, digital competence is related to many 21st-century skills that should be acquired by all citizens. This will ensure their active participation in society.

Digital competence is the “*confident, critical and creative use of ICT to achieve goals related to work, employability, learning, leisure, inclusion and/or participation in society*” (Ferrari, 2013). Therefore, digital competence involves the confident and critical use of information society technology (IST) and, thus, basic skills in information and communication technology (ICT): the use of computers to retrieve, assess, store, produce, present and exchange information, and to communicate and participate in collaborative networks via the internet (European Union, 2006).

Hence, digital competence helps us understand and actively participate in our society; in the same way, it allows us to establish support networks for lifelong learning.

One risk related to digital competence is the digital divide. The digital divide is the separation between those who use and are trained to use ICT and those who do not have access to these resources or having it; they do not know how to use them.

A digital divide is an economic inequality between groups, broadly construed, in terms of access to, use of, or knowledge of information and communication technologies (ICT) (Wikipedia)

Learning digital competence not only needs to be addressed as a subject but also should be embedded within teaching in all subjects. Building digital competence should start as early as possible by embedding and learning ICT, i.e., in primary education, by learning to use digital tools critically, confidently, and creatively, with attention paid to security, safety, and privacy.

Thus, we must remember that teachers should be equipped with digital competence to support this process. Mastery of digital competencies gives us opportunities to access and produce information, share it, and communicate through ICT simultaneously, allowing us to implement different learning methodologies.

There are five areas that integrate digital competence. These areas are (Ferrari, 2013):

- **Information:** identify, locate, retrieve, store, organize and analyze digital information, judging its relevance and purpose.
- **Communication:** communicate in digital environments, share resources through online tools, link with others and collaborate through digital tools, interact with and participate in communities and networks, and cross-cultural awareness.
- **Content-creation:** Create and edit new content (from word processing to images and video); integrate and re-elaborate previous knowledge and content; produce creative expressions, media outputs and programming; deal with and apply intellectual property rights and licenses.
- **Safety:** personal protection, data protection, digital identity protection, security measures, safe and sustainable use.
- **Problem-solving:** identify digital needs and resources, make informed decisions as to which are the most appropriate digital tools according to the purpose or need, solve conceptual problems through digital means, creatively use technologies, solve technical problems, and update one's own and others' competencies.

The information, communication and content-creation areas are linear, while safety and problem-solving areas are more transversal. This means that while information, communication and content-creation areas deal with competencies that can be re-traced in terms of specific activities and uses, safety and problem-solving areas apply to any

activity carried out through digital means.

Tomorrow's illiterate will not be the man who can't read; he will be the man who has not learned how to learn. The new education must teach the individual how to classify and reclassify information, how to evaluate its veracity, how to change categories when necessary, how to move from the concrete to the abstract and back, how to look at problems from a new direction — how to teach himself. Tomorrow's illiterate will not be the man who can't read; he will be the man who has not learned how to learn. (Alvin Toffler)

TEACHING WITH AND THROUGH ICT

The Swedish Curriculum (<http://www.skolverket.se>) notes as “goals to attain” in the compulsory school to:

- Have some knowledge of the media and of their role in relation to the media.
- Be able to use information technology as a tool in their search for knowledge.

To develop this knowledge and skills in our students, we must increase the use of ITC. Despite this increase in the use of ICT, we need to know that an advance in digital competence does not automatically follow the addition of ICT tools to schools. Thus, we should put into practice methods that join contents, methodologies, and resources that permit the development of digital competence in our students.

We need to be trained in skills related to pedagogical applications of ICT, not only in skills related to tool operation. Technical skills constitute a basic part of the complex concept of digital competence, but they are not the only part.

As Krumsvik (2011) notes, teachers' digital competence is proficient in using ICT in their professional context. This requires having good

pedagogic-didactic judgment and detailed knowledge of the implications of their decisions in the learning process and the digital development of their pupils and students.

Education programs, methodologies, frameworks, approaches, or models are usually related to a range of issues, such as: How will I teach? What will I teach? What are the contents that I will teach? How do I want to teach? What tools can I use?

From our point of view, we should change the focus from how I teach to how they learn or the way that I can help them learn. (Methodological changes). Therefore, we can support that using ICT in education promotes, among others, digital competence development, although it requires changes in the methodological models.

Before we continue, I would like to give you some tips in relation to teaching through ITC:

- **Change your point of view.** Focus your teaching in how your students learn instead of how you teach.
- **We need solid training and good support, but we do not know how or where to get it.** Develop a consistent Personal Learning Environment (PLE).
- **Technology does not solve all problems or make teachers better. Using ICT does not guarantee digital competence development.** In some cases, we use ICT the same way we use traditional tools, and we do not take advantage of their potential.
- **Do not throw out your curriculum.** We must integrate ICT into our curriculum and syllabuses. Curriculum and syllabuses are the reference, the framework, and not the ICT. You do not need to do it all at once. To use ICT, you need to feel confident and comfortable with it.
- **You do not have to be successful the first time, and you do not have to be afraid of failing.** Training, planning, designing, testing, and assessment are your tools, and failure is part of our

professional development.

- **Do not have to rush.** A long journey begins with one step. Begin with small changes; after these, when you have enough confidence, go ahead and introduce more.

TPACK

There are different models for promoting the integration of ICT in teaching. One of the most popular is the TPACK framework. The TPACK framework has been developed by Koehler and Mishra (more information at www.tpack.org) and extends Shulman's idea of pedagogical content knowledge.

This model introduces the Technological knowledge factor in Shulman's idea of Pedagogical and Content knowledge. The TPACK is the acronym for "Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge" and, therefore, is based on three primary areas of knowledge. TPACK is not a brand-new idea, nor is it owned by anyone. A range of scholars have argued that knowledge about technology cannot be treated as context-free and that good teaching requires understanding how technology relates to the pedagogy and content.

The TPACK framework is gaining popularity among researchers and scholars. This makes tracking its progress difficult, but for those getting started, the seminal description of TPACK (by that particular name) can be found in Mishra & Koehler (2006).

TPACK emphasizes the kinds of knowledge that lie at the intersections between of Content, Pedagogical and Technological areas, uncovering four knowledge bases teachers applicable to teaching. The components of TPACK (Koehler & Mishra, 2009) are:

- **Content Knowledge:** Teachers' knowledge about the subject matter to be learned or taught. The content to be covered in middle school science or history differs from that in an undergraduate course on art appreciation or a graduate seminar on astrophysics... As Shulman (1986) noted, this knowledge would include knowledge of concepts, theories, ideas, organizational frameworks, evidence and proof, and established practices and approaches toward developing such knowledge.
- **Pedagogical Knowledge:** Teachers' deep knowledge about the processes and practices or teaching and learning methods. It encompasses, among other things, overall educational purposes, values, and aims. This generic form of knowledge

applies to understanding how students learn, general classroom management skills, lesson planning, and student assessment.

- **Technology Knowledge:** Knowledge about specific ways of thinking about and working with technology, tools, and resources. This knowledge includes understanding ICTs broadly enough to apply them productively at work and in everyday life, recognizing when ICT can assist or impede the achievement of a goal, and adapting to changes in ICT.
- **Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK):** Knowledge of pedagogy applicable to teaching specific content. The transformation of the contents for teaching is very important for teachers. This transformation occurs as the teacher interprets the content, finds multiple ways to represent it, and adapts and tailors the instructional materials to alternative conceptions of students' knowledge (Shulman, 1986). Pedagogical Content Knowledge covers the core of teaching, learning, curriculum, assessment and reporting, such as the conditions that promote learning and the links among curriculum, assessment and pedagogy.
- **Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)** is an understanding of the way in which technology and content influence and constrain one another. Teachers need to master more than the content they teach; they must have a deep understanding of the way in which this content (or the kinds of representations that can be constructed) can be changed by applying certain technologies. Understanding the impact of technology on the practice and knowledge of a given discipline is critical to developing or selecting the appropriate technological tools for educational purposes.
- **Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)** is an understanding of how teaching and learning can change when

certain technologies are used in specific ways. This includes knowing the pedagogical affordances and constraints of various technological tools related to pedagogical designs and strategies.

- **Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK):** it requires an understanding of the representation of concepts using technologies; pedagogical techniques that use technologies in constructive ways to teach content; knowledge of what makes concepts difficult or easy to learn and how technology can help redress some of the problems that students face; knowledge of students' prior knowledge and theories of epistemology; and knowledge of how ICTs can be used to build on existing knowledge in order to develop new epistemologies or strengthen the old ones.

Hence, TPACK is more than joining the knowledge of the three areas individually, and we can consider it as the basis for effective teaching through technology.

Finally, we would like to express our commitment to developing teacher training programs that link pedagogical, content, and technological knowledge to develop our students' (digital) competencies.

PRACTICAL LESSON

Using the TPACK framework (learning activity types) as a reference, think and design content and a pedagogical strategy to develop through easy software such as *Hotpotatoes*.

WHAT IS HOT POTATOES?

The Hot Potatoes suite includes six applications, enabling you to create interactive multiple-choice, short-answer, jumbled-sentence, crossword, matching/ordering, and gap-fill exercises for the World Wide Web. Hot Potatoes is freeware; you may use it for any purpose or project. It is not open source. The Java version provides all the features found in the Windows version, except you can't upload to hotpotatoes.net, and you can't export a SCORM object from Java Hot Potatoes.

You can download Hot Potatoes from:

- [Hot Potatoes 6.3 installer](#) (Hot Potatoes for Windows 98/ME/NT4/2000/XP/Vista, version 6.3).
- [Hot Potatoes for Linux users running Wine \(version 6.3\)](#). This is a zip file containing the folder structure of the Windows version of Hot Potatoes. You can extract this to create the HotPot program folder without running the setup program.

Download Java Hot Potatoes:

- [Download Java Hot Potatoes](#) on Mac OS X, Windows, Linux or any computer running a Java Virtual Machine. To install and run Java Hot Potatoes on Mac OS X:
 1. Download the file javahotpot61.zip from the link above.
 2. Unzip that file on your laptop; you will have a folder called JavaHotPot6.
 3. Drag the JavaHotPot6 folder to the Applications directory

on your computer.

4. Open the folder and double-click the JavaHotPotatoes6 application icon.
5. Trash the javahotpot61.zip file.

When you first start up Hot Potatoes, it will ask you for your username. This name is stored on your computer and not sent to anyone; it will be inserted into your exercises to identify you as the author. You must provide a username before you can use all the features of Hot Potatoes.

Hot potatoes's interface

Here is a [Tutorial in Swedish](http://www.vasa.abo.fi/pf/projekt/dako/guide/hotpotatoes/) developed by Fredrik Åman at the Faculty of Education. Åbo Akademi University, Vasa (<http://www.vasa.abo.fi/pf/projekt/dako/guide/hotpotatoes/>).

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TPACK Game: <http://training.learnon.nl/tpackgame/index.php>

TPACK.org; <http://www.tpack.org/>

